

Functional evaluation of blood cells using a shear flow generator and fluorescence imaging

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Platelets are one of the blood cells that play an important role in hemostasis in the human body. Many previous studies have revealed a close relationship between fluid stimulation by shear flow and platelet function. In our laboratory, we have developed a custom made shear flow generator for blood cells. In our previous studies, we combined such shear flow generator with fluorescence imaging of platelets. As a result, we have revealed changes in platelet function associated with bleeding disorders in artificial hearts. Furthermore, in recent years, platelets have been used in research as carriers for drug delivery systems. Focusing on this recent trend, we hypothesized that applying shear flow stimulation to platelets would increase the amount of drug loaded. There, platelets and fluorescent dextran, which resembled a drug, were incubated while being exposed to fluid force stimulation in a shear flow generator. Subsequently, the amount of fluorescent dextran uptake into platelets was evaluated using a confocal microscope and a flow cytometer. The results revealed that stimulation of shear flow increased drug loading into platelets. In the future, our laboratory will further elucidate the functions of platelets by combining shear flow generators and fluorescence imaging techniques.

Keywords: platelet, blood cells, shearing device, shear flow, fluorescence imaging